

COMPATATIVE ANALYSIS OF PRAISE IN ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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Abstract:

This article examines the linguistic and cultural features of praise in English and Russian languages. Praise is considered an important element of communication that reflects social norms, values, and interpersonal relationships within different cultures. Russian and English cultures have distinctive national characteristics when it comes to compliments. It is determined that compliments are frequently encountered in English and Russian, emphasizing intellectual, professional, and moral aspects of appearance and personality. It is uncommon to find compliments that highlight someone's deeds and physical prowess. Compared to English, Russian compliments are more sentimental and frequently include emotionally charged words. A compliment is typically employed in dialogical discourse since it conveys attention and concern.

Keywords:

praise, approval, types of compliments, national specificity, intercultural communication, means of expression.

Introduction

Language plays a crucial role in human communication, allowing people to express emotions, attitudes, and evaluations. One of the most important communicative strategies used in everyday interaction is praise. Praise is used to evaluate an object in the surrounding reality. Every person is both the object of evaluation and the subject of evaluation, as they determine the positive and negative properties of an object, assigning it a value. In any language, there are various lexical, syntactic, and morphological means of expressing compliments. Compliments have become an essential part of speech etiquette, reflecting the communicative behavior of representatives of a particular culture and its national characteristics. When studying another culture, it is necessary to know in which situations compliments are appropriate and how best to express them in order to avoid mistakes and misunderstandings in communication.

Attempts to study evaluative statements have already been made in linguistics. Compliments and praise are classified as the most important speech genres with positive evaluative semantics. Researchers study various aspects of compliments. For example, speech tactics and gender aspects were examined by Z.F. Sungatullina and T.I. Radikova, while strategies for forming compliments were studied by N.A. Kapura and S.D. Gribakina [Сунгатуллина, Радикова, 2021, Kapura, Gribakina, 2018]. The national specifics of compliments in different cultures were examined by O.V. Kubaeva and Z.N. Isaeva, H. Liu, N.I. Shadmanova, and M.A. Yarmatova [Kubaeva, Liu H, 2024; Shadmanova, 2024]. M.N. Vrazhnova and L.O. Ternovaya wrote about the pedagogical impact of compliments, while K.O. Tsakhilova studied the socio-psychological functions of compliments [Vrazhnova, 2023; Tsakhilova, 2024].

Praise can be defined as a verbal (and/or nonverbal) expression of approval in language and speech. The English noun "praise" etymologically goes back to the Latin noun "pretium," which means 'value' or "worth." Everything that is highly valued or worthy of praise is often described in English with the adjective "precious," which comes from the same Latin root.

As mentioned earlier, there is currently no clear definition of a compliment. Some researchers define it as a speech act aimed at communication, others as the main characteristic of a person's behavior, and still others as an exaggeration of a person's merits. Compliments are often associated with praise, although there is no clear distinction between the two. According to R.V. Serebryakova, a compliment is a speech act that elicits a positive response from the interlocutor, in which the interlocutor's merits may be exaggerated, and it is very emotional. Praise is a speech act that serves as approval, is formulated briefly, and does not imply a response from the interlocutor. However, in some cases, praise can have the characteristics of a compliment and vice versa [Serebryakova,2002]. In a compliment, considered as a speech act, three main aspects should be distinguished: speech action, psychological interaction, and the manner of linguistic realization of speech action. The speech action model integrates the provisions of speech act theory, speech activity theory, and the concept of politeness. We understand a compliment as a linguistic means of achieving qualitatively different (speech and non-speech) communicative goals, as the realization of a speech act, which is a complex unity of a locutionary act, an illocutionary act, a perlocutionary act, and a social act.

A.S. Leonova noted the following situations in which the British resort to compliments and praise: 1) when meeting someone new; 2) to boost the self-esteem of the person they are talking to; 3) to establish contact; 4) to confess love; 5) to maintain friendly relations. In Russian culture, compliments are often used to show care and attention, to manipulate, to express positive feelings, to convince the interlocutor that something does not particularly suit or appeal to them [Леонова,2023].

In Russian communication culture, compliments about a person's appearance prevail, while in English communication culture, compliments about a person's inner, moral qualities take precedence. The main factors determining these national and cultural differences in the use of compliments are the dissimilarity of hierarchical value systems in the compared linguistic cultures and differences in the principles and norms of Russian and English etiquette culture. However, in English speech communication, compliments on appearance are also given considerable attention—this type of compliment ranks second in English culture. It is quite obvious that in both Russian and English communicative cultures, compliments on appearance are used mainly in informal communication situations. In business communication, compliments about the appearance of the interlocutor are rarely used and may be considered a sign of bad taste.

Here are some examples of such statements taken from Russian and English literary works:

«Ты красива, и к тому же в его вкусе...» (Щемелинин К.С. «Я»)

I've always wanted to meet you, she gushes. Then she stands back and says, You are as pretty as everyone says (Bushnell C. Four Blondes)

In the examples above, compliments are used in reference to the addressee's overall look or that of a third party who is not a part of the discussion. In both Russian and English, compliments regarding specific aspects of appearance, like bodily parts, are frequently utilized. These compliments describe the face, hair, hands, eyes, etc.

«Бог мой, я ведь и не представлял, какие у тебя красивые глаза! - вдруг сказал он. - Цвета моря» (Королева А. «Глаза цвета моря»)

You have really nice eyes, dont you? Misshaped though, but nice (Ostdick N. Ronald Jones Loves Me)

Kindness and other traditional virtues, such as generosity, honesty, modesty, courage, and religiosity, are the most productive types of compliments about a person's inner, moral qualities, which are used more frequently in English speech than other types of speech acts of praise/compliment.

«Dear Sally, what I like about you is your beautiful honesty (Lessing D. England Versus England) »

«Youve been wonderfully kind to me (Wharton E. Summer) ...they are some of the finest and the kindest human beings on the face of the earth! (Wharton E. Summer) »

If the evaluation of a person's moral qualities—traditional virtues—is expressed explicitly in English examples (you are an honest man, you've been kind, she is very brave), then the qualities we describe are also valued in Russian expressions of praise and compliments of this type, though they are not always named directly and may be positioned as characteristics that set the person receiving the compliment apart from others. Let's contrast:

«Это очень хороший мальчик. Серьезный, добрый, честный» (Маринина А. «Стечение обстоятельств»)

«Что мне еще в тебе, Матвей, нравится, так это то, что ты в партии модные не стремишься, на себя только и надеешься» (Доценко В. «Правосудие Бешеного»)

Conclusion

Thus, the study demonstrated that compliments that emphasize a person's moral, professional, and intellectual attributes in addition to their attractiveness are frequently given in both English and Russian. It is far less frequent to compliment someone on their deeds and physical prowess.

Considering the cultural and national specifics of compliments, it can be observed that Russian compliments are more emotional than English ones because they are accompanied by emotionally charged vocabulary, repetitions, comparisons, adjectives in the superlative degree of comparison, and exclamations. Since compliments are mostly utilized in dialogical speech to demonstrate attention and concern, they are not frequently seen in artistic works as speech actions.

References:

1. Vrazhnova M.N., Ternovaya L.O. Compliment in everyday communication and pedagogical impact // Cossacks. 2023. No. 71 (6). – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/kompliment-v-povsednevnom-obschenii-i-pedagogicheskom-vozdeystvii> (accessed 10.07.2024)
2. Kapura N.V., Gribakina S.D. Strategies of compliment formation in Russian- and English speaking culture // Concept. 2018. № 3. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/strategii-formirovaniya-komplimentov-v-russkoyazychnoy-i-angloyazychnoy-kulture> (accessed 10.07.2024).
3. Kubaeva O.V., Isayeva Z.N. Main types of compliments in Russian and Tsakhur languages // Izvestiya DSPU. Social and Humanities. 2018. No. 2. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/osnovnye-tipy-komplimentov-v-russkom-i-tsahurskom-yazykah> 10.07.2024).

4. Liu H. Functions of compliment in Russian and Chinese speech etiquette // Russian Linguistic Bulletin. 2023. No. 3 (39). – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/funktsii-komplimenta-v-russkom-i-kitayskom-rechevom-etikete> (accessed 10.07.2024).
5. Леонова А.С. Лингвокультурологический анализ мужских и женских комплиментов в русской и английской лингвокультурах // Актуальные проблемы гуманитарных и естественных наук. 2015. № 8-2. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/lingvokulturologicheskiy-analiz-muzhskih-i-zhenskih-komplimentov-v-russkoy-i-angliyskoy-lingvokulturah> (дата обращения 13.11.2023).
6. Serebryakova R.V. National specificity of speech acts of compliment and praise in Russian and English communicative cultures // PhD of Philology Dis. Voronezh, 2002. 202 p.
7. Сунгатуллина З.Ф., Радикова Т.И. Речевые тактики комплимента и ответа на комплимент: гендерный аспект // СибСкрипт. 2021. № 2 (86). – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/rechevye-taktiki-komplimenta-i-otveta-na-kompliment-gendernyy-aspekt> (дата обращения 10.07.2024).
8. Tsakhilova K.O. Social and psychological functions of compliment in interpersonal communication // Innovative Science: Psychology, Pedagogy, Defectology. 2021. № 1. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/sotsialno-psihologicheskie-funktsii-komplimenta-v-mezhlichnostnom-obschenii> (accessed 10.07.2024).
9. Shadmanova N.I., Yarmatova M.A. National specificity of Russian and Uzbek compliments // Academic research in educational sciences. 2021. No. 4. – URL: <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/natsionalnaya-spetsifika-russkih-i-uzbekskih-komplimentov> (accessed 10.07.2024)